

Viscosity and Density of Solutions of Dichloroacetic Acid in Ethanol and Nitrobenzene and in their Mixtures at different Temperatures[†]

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Viscosities and densities at 25, 30, 35 and 40° are reported for dichloroacetic acid (DCAA) in ethanol, nitrobenzene and ethanol-nitrobenzene mixtures. The data have been used to calculate viscosity *B*-coefficients employing Jones-Dole, Breslau-Miller and Vand equations. Apparent molar volumes have also been obtained from density measurements. Results show that DCAA can be approximated as spherical entities in ethanol-nitrobenzene mixtures and acts as structure-promoter.

DEPENDENCE of viscosity and apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) on concentration (*C*) of solute and temperature (*T*) of solutions has been employed as a tool to study ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions in some non-aqueous mixed solvents. It has been found by a number of workers¹ that the addition of electrolyte could either break or make the structure of a liquid. Since viscosity is a property of the liquid which depends upon the intermolecular forces, the structural aspects of the liquid can be inferred from the viscosity of solutions at different concentrations and temperatures. In our earlier communications²⁻⁵ we reported the effect of addition of monochloroacetic acid on the structures of mixed solvents. While interpreting viscosity and apparent molar volume data of solutions prepared in mixed solvents, the mutual interaction of solvent molecules have not been taken into consideration⁶.

One such system where there exists a mutual interaction between solvent molecules, forming clusters of varying compositions and sizes, such as are present in the critical solution region is ethanol-nitrobenzene^{7,8}. The present investigation is undertaken to examine the effect of addition of DCAA on the mutual interaction between ethanol and nitrobenzene molecules.

Experimental

DCAA was kept over anhydrous MgSO₄ for 8 h and fractionally distilled. Ethanol⁹ and nitrobenzene¹⁰, purified by standard methods, were mixed (by weight) to give mixtures of different compositions. Solutions of different molarities were prepared afresh by dissolving the acid in solvent mixtures and kept for some time. Care was taken to prevent photolysis of DCAA solutions. The

experimental set-up and methods used for measuring densities and viscosities of solutions were similar to those reported earlier²⁻⁵. The reproducibility in density and viscosity measurement was ± 0.0001 g ml⁻¹ and ± 0.003 cp respectively. The temperature measurements were accurate within $\pm 0.01^\circ$. For viscosity measurement, the time of efflux of a constant volume of the liquid through the capillary of Ostwald viscometer was measured with the help of stop-watch correct to 0.01 s. The efflux time for all liquids at all temperatures was always greater than 100 s, hence kinetic energy correction to viscosity measurement was not necessary.

Results and Discussion

Density (ρ), viscosity (η) and relative viscosity (η_r) of DCAA solutions in different compositions of ethanol-nitrobenzene at 25, 30, 35 and 40° were determined. The values obtained are found to vary with the concentration of DCAA and temperature of measurement. It is evident from the data that the values of viscosities (η) of DCAA solutions in different compositions of ethanol-nitrobenzene increase with increasing concentration of the acid and decrease with increasing temperature.

The variation of η_r with concentration (*C*) is usually expressed by the Jones-Dole equation,

$$\eta_r = 1 + AC^{1/2} + BC \quad (1)$$

Since in general, $A/B \ll 1$, the second term may be neglected at concentrations above 0.002 *M*, and equation (1) may be written as¹¹

$$\eta_r = 1 + BC, \quad 0.002 \text{ M} < C < \sim 0.1 \text{ M} \quad (2)$$

In the present study, equation (2) is valid in solutions of concentration ranging between 0.008 and 0.12 *M*. Fig. 1 shows the linear plots of η_r vs *C*, indicating

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Fig. 1. Plots of η_r vs C for DCAA in different compositions of ethanol-nitrobenzene at 25°: (1) nil, (2) 20, (3) 40, (4) 60, (5) 80 and (6) 100 wt% ethanol.

Fig. 2. Plots of $(\eta_r)^2$ vs C^2 for DCAA in different compositions of ethanol-nitrobenzene at 25°. explanation same as in Fig. 1.

the applicability of equation (2). The values of B obtained from the slopes of the plots are given in Table 1. The relative viscosity data of solutions having concentration greater than 0.12 M have been fitted into following equations.

(i) Moulik equation¹²,

$$\eta_r = M + K' C^2 \quad (3)$$

where M and K' are constants. The applicability of Moulik equation is shown by the linear plots of η_r^2 vs C^2 (Fig. 2).

(ii) Breslau-Miller equation¹¹,

$$\bar{V}_0 = \frac{-2.5 + [(2.5 C)^2 - 4(10.05 C^2) (1 - \eta_r)]^{1/2}}{2(10.05) C^2} \quad (4)$$

where \bar{V}_0 is the average effective rigid molar volume. The values of \bar{V}_0 thus obtained were used for calculating B -coefficients, employing the relation,

$$B = 2.90 \bar{V}_0 e^{-0.018} \quad (5)$$

(iii) Vand's equation¹³,

$$\ln \eta_r = \frac{2.5 \phi}{1 - K\phi} \quad (6)$$

where ϕ is volume fraction and K the generalised particle interaction coefficient. Substituting $\phi = C\bar{V}$ and rearranging equation (6), we get,

$$\frac{C}{\log \eta_r} = \frac{2.303}{2.5\bar{V}} - \frac{1.303}{2.5} KC \quad (7)$$

where \bar{V} is the effective flowing volume. \bar{V} has been obtained from the intercept of the linear plot of $C/\log \eta_r$ vs C (Fig. 3). B -coefficients are calculated from the relation,

$$B = 2.5 \bar{V} \quad (8)$$

B values thus calculated from equation (2), (5) and (8) are listed in Table 1 for comparison. B values obtained from Breslau-Miller and Vand equations are more or less identical, however they differ

Fig. 3. Plots of $C/\log \eta_r$ vs C for DCAA in different compositions of ethanol-nitrobenzene at 25° : explanation same as in Fig. 1.

considerably from those obtained from Jones-Dole equation (2). This discrepancy as regards to the magnitude of B may be attributed to concentration dependence validity of viscosity equations and variable ion-solvent interaction with varying concentration of electrolyte. The familiar viscosity B -coefficients and the related ionic molar contribution to the free energy, enthalpy and entropy of activation are re-examined on the compensation principle by Feakins *et al.*¹⁴. Particular attention is paid to the nature of the solvent in the transition state. If compensation between enthalpic and entropic contributions from solute-induced structural changes occurs in both ground and transition state solvents, then free energy of activation, and hence B cannot be influenced by changes in the structure of the solvent of the type proposed, say, by Frank and Wen. Instead it is suggested that in aqueous solution, an ion can coordinate more solvent molecules in the more weakly bonded transition state solvent than in the ground state solvent. Even if the compensation principle is not accepted, this explanation removes structural changes in the solvent as a unique explanation of the observed trends in B -coefficients. However, close examination of our data (Table 1) shows that B values are

positive and decrease with increase in temperature (negative dB/dT) suggesting¹⁵ structure-promoting tendency of DCAA. The positive B values and negative dB/dT show the absence of a firm layer of solvent molecules around the ion in their co-sphere.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF B^* FROM VARIOUS EQUATIONS

Ethanol % (w/w) in solvent	25°			30°		
	B^a	B^b	B^c	B^a	B^b	B^c
00	0.192	0.150	0.153	0.172	0.110	0.121
20	0.162	0.153	0.155	0.159	0.127	0.105
40	0.219	0.176	0.198	0.199	0.168	0.180
60	0.162	0.127	0.135	0.156	0.115	0.116
80	0.196	0.150	0.163	0.184	0.139	0.143
100	0.245	0.182	0.192	0.208	0.159	0.178
	35°			40°		
00	0.164	0.109	0.127	0.155	0.098	0.106
20	0.150	0.124	0.105	0.146	0.121	0.095
40	0.143	0.156	0.170	0.141	0.144	0.165
60	0.098	0.118	0.111	0.094	0.104	0.108
80	0.133	0.130	0.142	0.180	0.124	0.140
100	0.194	0.150	0.177	0.181	0.144	0.168

*Obtained from: ^a η_r vs C curve; ^bBreslau-Miller's eqn.; ^c $B = 2.5 \bar{V}$.

The apparent molar volumes are calculated using the equation,

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000(\rho_0 - \rho)}{C\rho_0} + \frac{M_2}{\rho_0} \quad (9)$$

where ρ and ρ_0 are the densities of solution and solvent respectively, C is molarity and M_2 the molecular weight of the solute. The limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_v°) which is equal to the partial molar volume at infinite dilution (\bar{V}_2°) is obtained by extrapolating ϕ_v vs C curves (Fig. 4) to zero concentration, neglecting the points at low concentration which deviated considerably from linearity. The same procedure was adopted by Franks *et al.*¹⁶ and Kaulgud and Dhondge¹⁷ because of the possibility of systematic error at low concentration due to the dissolved air in solution. \bar{V}_2° of CHCl_2COOH in nitrobenzene, ethanol and ethanol-nitrobenzene at 25, 30, 35 and 40° are listed in Table 2. \bar{V}_2° of DCAA is the sum of its ionic partial molar volumes¹⁸, $\bar{V}_{\text{H}^+}^\circ$ and $\bar{V}_{\text{CHCl}_2\text{COO}^-}^\circ$ as

$$\bar{V}_{\text{CHCl}_2\text{COOH}}^\circ = \bar{V}_{\text{H}^+}^\circ + \bar{V}_{\text{CHCl}_2\text{COO}^-}^\circ \quad (10)$$

When such a solute is introduced into a polar solvent, the partial molar volume of the solute at infinite dilution (\bar{V}_2°), can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{V}_{\text{CHCl}_2\text{COOH}}^\circ &= \bar{V}_{\text{H}^+}^\circ + \bar{V}_{\text{CHCl}_2\text{COO}^-}^\circ \\ &= V_{\text{H}^+(\text{int})}^\dagger + V_{\text{CHCl}_2\text{COO}^-(\text{int})}^\dagger + \Delta V \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $V_{\text{H}^+(\text{int})}^\dagger$ and $V_{\text{CHCl}_2\text{COO}^-(\text{int})}^\dagger$ are intrinsic volumes of the ions and ΔV is the change in volume of the system due to ion-solvent interaction. The values of $\bar{V}_{\text{CHCl}_2\text{COOH}}^\circ$ in nitrobenzene are higher than these in ethanol (Table 2) and in water¹⁹. \bar{V}_2° values of DCAA in ethanol and water are very

Fig. 4. Plots of ϕ_v vs C for DCAA in different compositions of ethanol-nitrobenzene at 25°: explanation same as in Fig. 1.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF ϕ_v^0 ($=\bar{V}_2^0$) AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

Ethanol % (w/w) in solvent	ϕ_v^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)			
	25°	30°	35°	40°
00	93.75	92.50	90.00	85.00
20	92.50	92.00	82.50	80.25
40	49.50	40.00	39.50	37.00
60	197.45	195.25	195.00	192.50
80	59.50	62.50	78.75	80.00
100	68.40	68.80	70.40	74.90

close and lower than those in nitrobenzene. This suggests that solvation is comparatively stronger in water and ethanol than in nitrobenzene. It has been assumed by earlier authors^{19,20,21} that in electrolytic solutions the anion solvation can be considered as negligible. They argued that the solvation number at infinite dilution is really a measure of the extent to which the cation is solvated. Extending these arguments to solutions of DCAA in pure nitrobenzene and ethanol, it can be assumed that in the case of dichloroacetate ion due to its large size ($\bar{V}_{\text{CHCl}_2\text{COO}^-}$) has negligible

solvation in comparison to the proton. In other words, the ΔV term in equation (11) is mainly due to proton solvation. The solvation of proton of CHCl_2COOH will then take the most effective role in the volume change due to structural alteration arising from ion-solvent interactions. So the lower values of \bar{V}_2^0 of DCAA in the ethanol and water suggest that \bar{V}_{H^+} is smaller in ethanol and water than it is in nitrobenzene. This reveals that relative to nitrobenzene, both ethanol and water are prone to be held more compactly around H^+ ion.

In ethanol-nitrobenzene mixtures, the above structural arrangement is complicated by other associated factors such as (i) preferential solvation²²⁻²⁴ of the ions by the different species present in the solvent system and (ii) interactions^{7,8} between the molecules of ethanol and nitrobenzene. The change of partial molar volumes with varying proportion of the other solvents in ethanol in the case of electrolytes has been observed earlier by other workers^{19,25-27}. Bateman²⁵ assigned this change of the partial molar volumes, \bar{V}_2^0 with composition of the mixed solvent to variable solvation of the ions. When solvation occurs, the ion complex may be assumed to be packed differently in different media and stronger the packing, the smaller is the molar volume. It has been observed that \bar{V}_2^0 of DCAA has minimum and maximum values at 40 and 60 wt% ethanol respectively and similar observations in the values of partial molar volume have also been reported^{19,27,28}. It has been suggested that around 40 wt% ethanol the structure formation between the two kinds of the solvent molecules is the most enhanced, and in this solvent mixture due to the preformed holes (or availability of solvent free volume) into which the anion ($\text{CHCl}_2\text{COO}^-$) may fit without the prerequisite of hole formation prior to dissolution, \bar{V}_2^0 becomes minimum. At 60 wt% ethanol where \bar{V}_2^0 becomes maximum, the competition between pure nitrobenzene and pure ethanol structure results in the mixture having essentially a close packed structure^{7,8} with consequent minimum free volume. Thus there are no preformed holes in the binary solvent and dissolution of the third component solute required maximum expansion of the solvent to accommodate the solute.

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